

DIGITAL LEARNING FUNCTIONALITY IN RELATION TO CRITICAL THINKING DISPOSITION OF TECHNICAL, VOCATIONAL AND LIVELIHOOD STUDENTS

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the relationship between digital learning functionality and critical thinking disposition of public senior high school Technology and Livelihood Education (TVL) students. This study utilized the descriptive-correlational design with 150 respondents selected using simple random sampling. In gathering data, the researcher adapted a survey questionnaire both for the digital learning functionality and critical thinking disposition. Ethical considerations were observed in data collection. The collated data were subjected to statistical treatments that were used to analyze the data gathered. Findings showed that the digital learning functionality of TVL students was extensive, which means that their digital learning functionality was oftentimes observed. The critical thinking disposition of TVL students was extensive, which means that their critical thinking disposition was oftentimes observed. There was a high significant relationship between students' digital learning functionality and critical thinking disposition. The domains of digital learning functionality that influenced the critical thinking disposition of TVL students were technology knowledge and technological content knowledge. With this, the Department of Education should boost the implementation of programs related to improving the 21st literacy skills of learners, particularly by heightening the activities pertaining to digital learning functionality.

KEY WORDS

1. Digital learning functionality
2. critical thinking disposition
3. technology knowledge
4. technological content knowledge

1. Introduction

Many senior high school Technology, Vocational and Livelihood (TVL) students have difficulties understanding the lesson during the resumption of face-to-face classes, which is caused by poor reading comprehension and mathematical skills, difficulty in following instructions and low self-esteem. This situation resulted to low critical thinking disposition skills among TVL students which hinder them to think critically and responsibly in facing academic challenges ahead. During the in-person classes, it is observed that students do not make an effort to get correct information as well as do not make an effort to find other alternatives, instead they just rely on what their teachers have imparted to them. In Indonesia, critical thinking disposition among students in technical and vocation education is low because it is influenced by the low self-confidence in the teaching and learning process particularly dur-

ing the return of the in-person classes (Wiradinata, Rosita Amalia, 2021). Fitriani, Asy' Ari, Zubaidah and Mahanal (2018) expressed that student's critical thinking disposition is low because they do not have self-confidence to accept learning challenges, as well as, they do not want to issue opinions as they do not believe in their abilities. Similarly, the finding of Syauqi, Munadi and Triyono (2020) showed that non-academic students in Southeast Asia have low critical thinking ability during the post-pandemic education, this indicates that they do not try to explore or learn additional learning material from other sources to support studies. During the resumption of face-to-face classes, some teachers in the Philippines observed that many senior high school students particularly in Technical, Vocational and Livelihood (TVL) track have low critical thinking disposition ability (Palavan, 2020). This is evident as they have difficulty in processing higher order thinking skills questions and even situational problems that need their ability to process and analyze (Fulgueras Bautista, 2020). Reyes-Chua et al. (2022) found that TVL students have low literacy skills such as reading comprehension and mathematical skills, difficulty in following basic instructions and low reasoning skills during the return of face-to-face classes. These problems confirmed being the reasons of having low critical thinking disposition skills among this group of senior high school students (Delosa Ong, 2021). The problem is also observable to the TVL students in Davao region. According to Farillon (2022), TVL students during the return of in-person classes are observed to have limited reasoning and analytical skills, as well as inability to provide evidence-based reasoning. These made them unable to apply critical thinking skills and problem-solving skills in daily life situations. The report of Sitchon (2022) showed that developing reading comprehension among TVL students in the region is one of the major problems during the resumption of face-to-face instruction. Teachers believed that this factor is the main reason why students have low critical thinking disposition ability. Hence, when these students are unequipped with critical thinking skills to face the challenges of 21st century learning, especially when they are dependable in any situation, would make them fail to process and solve real-life problems (Dela Peña, 2022). During the distance learning, one of the avenues for the students to acquire knowledge is through technology, in which improvement of their digital learning literacy is observable. However, when the face-to-face classes return, teachers observed that the critical thinking disposition of the TVL students is low. This is due to the learning gaps which is mainly caused by two years of distance learning because of the pandemic. In this manner, the researcher examined the extent of digital learning functionality as the major competency that might acquire during distance learning by TVL students and looked how it relates with their critical thinking disposition during the return of face-to-face instruction. Moreover, the researcher also determined which domains of digital learning functionality influenced the critical thinking disposition of TVL students. This study gave ideas to the Department of Education, Regional Director, Division Schools Superintendent, curriculum supervisor and school principals about the critical thinking disposition of TVL students, and if sustaining the digital learning functionality in the instruction would help to boost their critical thinking disposition.

The independent variable is the digital learning functionality which will be measured in terms of technology knowledge, technological content knowledge and technological instructional knowledge. The dependent variable is the critical thinking disposition which includes

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

the following indicators: planning, engagement, innovativeness and self-evaluation. It is the contention of the framework that digital learning functionality may have significant relationship to critical thinking disposition of TVL students. Moreover, determining which indicators of dig-

ital learning functionality (planning, engagement, innovativeness and self-evaluation) would significantly influence the critical thinking disposition of TVL students is the intent of the study.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research methods, which give direction in this investigation. It includes the research design, research respondents of the study, research instrument and the data gathering procedures.

2.1. Research Design—This chapter presents the method of the study which includes research design, respondents of the study, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis. In the preparation of this paper, the researcher employed artificial intelligence tools for proofreading. Specifically, AI was utilized to enhance the accuracy, coherence, and overall quality of the manuscript. This practice is being explicitly stated to maintain transparency and adhere to ethical standards in research. The usage of AI for proofreading reflects a commitment to leveraging advanced technologies responsibly and acknowledges the increasing prevalence and capability of AI in academic and professional writing. This study used the non-experimental quantitative method of research to gather data and information. The researcher can quantify the data to be collected and generalize findings from a sample to the target population by using the quantitative tech-

nique of research. Pratiwi (2017) highlighted that a quantitative methodology is one where the researcher primarily employs post-positivist arguments to generate information (cause-and-effect reasoning, reduction to specific variables and hypotheses and concerns, calculation and observation, and theory testing), surveys, and data collection on predetermined instruments that generate statistical data. Before collecting data, the researcher meticulously planned every part of the analysis since the data that need to gather were well understood. In quantitative research, the relationship between variables is looked at in order to evaluate goals. The data can then be evaluated using statistical techniques, and these variables can be calculated using instruments (Khaldi, 2017). This kind of method was appropriately used in the study because its purpose is to determine the relationship between digital learning functionality and critical thinking disposition of public

senior high school TVL students. The quantitative aspect of this study was also a suitable method for acquiring the information needed to ask the questions of the target respondents. The adapted questionnaires served as the foundation for data collection. Specifically, this study utilized the descriptive-correlational design to describe the relationship between or among variables. Doyle, Bryme and Brady (2009) pointed out that this design presented empirical data indicating the relationship between two or more factors. While Creswell (2008) claimed that it employed statistical models and forecasting approaches to comprehend and answer questions about the future. Since it measured and described the dependent and independent variables, the study was correlational in nature. Its objective was to identify and characterize the phenomena and to explain the relationships of variables. In this study, descriptive design was employed to investigate the extents of digital learning functionality and critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students. Furthermore, a correlational design was employed to assess the relationship between digital learning functionality and critical thinking disposition, as well as identification of digital learning functionality domains (technology knowledge, technological content knowledge and technological instructional knowledge) that influenced the critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students.

2.2. Research Respondents—In this study, the respondents were the selected one hundred fifty (150) public senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City. Moreover, the respondents to be part of the study are those who are currently enrolled in any strands under TVL track, attending the face-to-face classes and who have been attending distance learning; thus, they are selected as they are all expected being exposed to learning gaps caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. There were no age, sex, marital status, religion or ethnic-

ity restrictions in this study. On the other hand, simple random sampling technique was used in this study as the data collected by picking a certain number of respondents out of the total number of population in the sampling frame (Luthans, Youssef Avolio, 2018). In this study, selected public senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City were given the opportunity to give their rating on the extents of digital learning functionality and critical thinking disposition.

2.3. Research Instrument—The two variables of this study were measured using two instruments: the digital learning functionality questionnaire which consisted of three (3) domains such as technology knowledge, technological content knowledge and technological instructional knowledge was adapted from Vladova et al. (2021) and the critical thinking disposition questionnaire which consisted of four (4) domains such as planning, engagement, innovativeness and self-evaluation was adapted from Cahapay et al. (2021). The restructuring of items was carried out to make the instruments more applicable to the current local educational context. For validation, the survey questionnaire was forwarded to three (3) experts. A Validation Sheet was used by the three (3) experts to rate the Survey Questionnaire. All of the experts' opinions and recommendations were followed. Following the validity test, the survey questionnaire was piloted to twenty (20) public school senior high school students in Cabantuan National High School, Division of Davao City. Cronbach alpha was then used to assess its reliability. Items with Cronbach alpha values more than 0.70 were considered reliable, whereas items with values less than 0.70 were revised (Darren Mallery (1999) as cited in Wadkar, Singh, Argade Chakravarty, 2016). Digital Learning Functionality Questionnaire. Vladova et al. (2021) came up with this. It's a self-report questionnaire with a Likert scale that focuses on a detailed evaluation of the construct of digital

learning functionality in terms of technology and technological instructional knowledge. The knowledge, technological content knowledge rating scale for this attribute is as follows:

Table 1. Range of Means and Corresponding Descriptions

Range of Means	Description	Interpretation
4.21 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The digital learning functionality of public senior high school TVL students is always observed.
3.41 - 4.20	Extensive	The digital learning functionality of public senior high school TVL students is oftentimes observed.
2.61 - 3.40	Moderately Extensive	The digital learning functionality of public senior high school TVL students is sometimes observed.
1.81 - 2.60	Less Extensive	The digital learning functionality of public senior high school TVL students is rarely observed.
1.00 - 1.80	Not Extensive	The digital learning functionality of public senior high school TVL students is never observed.

Table 2. Range of Means and Corresponding Descriptions

Range of Means	Description	Interpretation
4.21 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students is always observed.
3.41 - 4.20	Extensive	The critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students is oftentimes observed.
2.61 - 3.40	Extensive	The critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students is sometimes observed.
1.81 - 2.60	Very Extensive	The critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students is rarely observed.
1.00 - 1.80	Extensive	The critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students is never observed.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The following steps were strictly followed in the conduct of the study.

- (1) **Permission to Conduct the Study.** The researcher asked an endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges with the consent of the thesis adviser to conduct the study. With the endorsement letter, the researcher sent a request letter to the DepeEd Division Office of Davao City through the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) to conduct the study. Then, the researcher asked permission to the school principals in Cluster 1 to gather data.
- (2) **Distribution and Retrieval of Survey Questionnaire.** Through the class ad-

visers, the researcher set a schedule to the respondents for the actual administration of the survey questionnaire. The researcher administered the survey questionnaire to the senior high school TVL students face-to-face, however, google form was considered upon the request of the respondents. With this, the researcher strictly abided the IATF health protocols at all times such as wearing of mask and social distancing.

- (3) **Collation and Statistical Treatment of the Study.** The data were tabulated and calculated following the successful administration and retrieval of the survey questionnaires. Then, to gather the essential data for interpretation and further analysis, relevant statistical tools were used.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The responses of the respondents were collated, tallied, tabulated, computed, presented, interpreted and analyzed employing the relevant statistical tools. In analyzing the result of the study, the researcher used the following statistical tools: Mean was used to measure the extent of digital learning functionality of public senior high school TVL students in terms of technology knowledge, technological content knowledge and technological instructional knowledge. This was also used to determine the extent of critical thinking disposition

of public senior high school TVL students in terms of planning, engagement, innovativeness and self-evaluation. Pearson's r was employed to determine if relationship exists between digital learning functionality and critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students. Multiple Linear Regression was utilized to determine which among the domains of digital learning functionality (technology knowledge, technological content knowledge and technological instructional knowledge) influenced the critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the findings and discussion based on the data gathered. The presentation is organized in four sections: first, digital learning functionality of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction; second, critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction; third, relationship between digital learning functionality and critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction; and fourth, domains of digital learning functionality that significantly influence the critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction.

Presented in Table 3 is the summary on the digital learning functionality of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction in terms of technology knowledge, technological content knowledge and technological instructional knowledge. It reveals that the domain “technology knowledge” obtained the highest mean value among the three (3) domains (\bar{x} =3.59) which is described as “extensive”, followed by the domain “technological content knowledge” (\bar{x} =3.54) which is described as “extensive”. However, the domain “technological instructional knowledge” obtained the lowest mean value among the three (3) domains (\bar{x} =3.51) which is described as “extensive”. It further reveals that the overall mean value on the extent of digital learning functionality of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction is 3.54 which is described as “extensive”. This indicates that the respondents’ technology knowledge, technological content knowledge and technological instructional knowledge are oftentimes observed. This

implies that the digital learning functionality of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction is oftentimes observed. The result is congruent to the idea of Sari and Keser (2021), who elaborated that students’ academic success is influenced by the continuous improvement of ICT. The current situation in the world has increased the need for ICT in terms of student learning due to the coronavirus breakdown. As a matter of fact, students represent a generation of digital groups for whom this steady switch from the real to the virtual world should not pose any operational challenge (Vladova et al., 20210). Camilleri (2021), however, stated that students differ according to discipline, such as subject matter or facets of digital literacy and competency, which should be considered when developing digital learning environments and approaches. The successful integration of technology into existing processes, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, can only be guaranteed if students demonstrate or develop appropriate attitudes, beliefs, behaviors, and habits (Sari s Keser, 2021).

Table 3. Summary on the Critical Thinking Disposition of Public Senior High School TVL Students in the Resumption of Face-to-face Instruction

No.	Domains of Critical Thinking Disposition	Mean	SD	Descriptive Equivalent
1.	Planning	3.60	0.95	Extensive
2.	Engagement	3.47	0.95	Extensive
3.	Innovativeness	3.61	0.87	Extensive
4.	Self-Evaluation	3.65	0.94	Extensive
OVERALL		3.58	0.93	Extensive

Shown in Table 3 is the summary on the critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction in terms of planning, engagement, innovativeness and self-evaluation. It reveals that the domain “self-evaluation” obtained the highest mean value among the four (4) domains (\bar{x} =3.65) which is described as “extensive”, followed by the domain “innovativeness”

(\bar{x} =3.61) which is described as “extensive”, while the domain “engagement” obtained the lowest mean value among the four (4) domains (\bar{x} =3.47) which is described as “extensive”. It reveals further that the overall mean value on the extent of critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students in the resump-

tion of face-to-face instruction is 3.58 which is described as “extensive”. This indicates that the planning, engagement, innovativeness and self-evaluation of the respondents are oftentimes observed. This implies that the critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction is oftentimes observed. According to Timmons et al. (2021), students who have a critical thinking disposition are open to diagnosing their learning needs, formulating learning goals, identifying human and material resources

for learning, selecting and putting into practice appropriate learning strategies, and assessing learning outcomes. Any educational method, including distance education, depends on having a strong critical thinking disposition. The allows students to connect educational theory and learning practice (Davies, 2017). In light of the COVID-19 conundrum (Ferri et al., 2020), an expanding body of academic works have recommended using efficient critical thinking strategies to reform distance learning in learners’ basic education.

Table 4. Relationship between Digital Learning Functionality and Critical Thinking Disposition of Public Senior High School TVL Students in the Face-to-face Instruction

Variables	Mean	SD	R	R²	Degree of Relationship	p-value	Decision @ 0.05 level
Digital Learning Functionality	3.54	0.93	2*0.77	2*0.59	2*High	2*0.000	2*Reject Ho
Critical Thinking Disposition	3.58	0.93					

Presented in Table 4 is the test of relationship between digital Learning functionality and critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction. It reveals that the relationship between digital Learning functionality and critical thinking disposition is high (R=0.77) and it is significant (p-value=0.000<0.05) at .05 level of significance. It shows that the digital Learning functionality significantly influenced the critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction.. This implies that when the digital learning functionality of public senior high school TVL students is always observed, they would have

high critical thinking disposition. It further reveals that 59 percent (R2=0.59) of the variance in critical thinking disposition can be attributed for the digital learning functionality of senior high school TVL students, while the other 41 percent is caused by other factors. This implies that the digital learning functionality may be helpful in increasing the critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students during the resumption of face-to-face instruction. The result is congruent to the findings of the study of Andyan et. (2020), who revealed that there is favorable and highly significant correlation between college students’ digital learning functionality and their critical thinking attitudes toward their performance in science labs.

The integration of digital learning features is the standard practice used to teach students critical thinking. Process skills or learning through discovery are fundamental inquiry skills because they help students make connections between their prior knowledge or concrete knowledge and new concepts. The capacity for indepen-

dent discovery and inquiry is more significant than the mastery of the concept that students learn. With the aid of technology, and most importantly when they are digitally functional, this discovery process can be accomplished (Farillon, 2022).

Summary on the Extent of Principle-Centered Effectiveness. Presented in table 1 shows the summary extent of principle-centered effectiveness of public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City. The indicator with highest mean is instructional program with a mean of (3.94), interpreted as extensive. It is then followed by financial and physical support had earned a mean of (3.84), which is also identified as extensive. Further, staff per-

sonnel administration had obtained a mean of (3.67) or extensive. Lastly, learner personnel administration has the least mean of (3.57), this also described as extensive. With an overall generated mean of (3.77) or extensive, therefore the summary extent of principle-centered effectiveness was extensive as perceived by public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City.

Table 5. Domains of Digital Learning Functionality that Influenced the Critical Thinking Disposition of Public Senior High School TVL Students in the Resumption of Face-to-face Instruction

Domains of Digital Learning Functionality	B	BE	Beta	t-stat	p-value	Decision
Constant	0.94	0.24		3.88	0.000	Significant
Technology Knowledge	0.21	0.07	0.24	2.68	0.009	Significant
Technological Content Knowledge	0.041	0.08	0.48	5.08	0.000	Significant
Technological Instructional Knowledge	0.13	0.07	0.16	1.71	0.091	Not Significant

Displayed in Table 5 is the test of influence of the domains of digital learning functionality towards the critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction. It reveals that at 0.05 level of confidence, technology knowledge (B=0.21, p-value=0.009<0.05) and technological content knowledge (B=0.41, p-value=0.000<0.05) significantly influenced the critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of

face-to-face instruction. It also shows that the relationship between digital learning functionality and critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students is high (R=0.77) and 59 percent (R²=0.59) of the variance in critical thinking disposition is attributed for digital learning functionality. It further shows that the model of critical thinking disposition is fit (F=42.71, p-value=0.000<0.05). The signs of statistically significant domains of digital learning functionality (technology knowledge and

technological content knowledge) are positive, indicating a direct positive relationship with critical thinking disposition. This means that when digital learning functionality is always observed by the public senior high school TVL students during the resumption of face-to-face classes, they would have high critical thinking disposition. Consistently, students' critical thinking abilities can be developed with the help of the critical thinking disposition. According to this viewpoint, they must be technologically literate in order to facilitate the development of critical thinking abilities. Therefore, being technologically literate and critical thinking traits among students are positively and significantly related (Boud Dawson, 2021). For instance, Khoza and Biyela (2020) stated that online learning can help students hone their critical thinking skills. The critical thinking disposition of each component cannot be said to be good or very good, so a better learning design, assignment, or online learning environment is required. Moreover, when technology knowledge is always observed by the public senior high school TVL students during the resumption of face-to-face classes, they would have high critical thinking disposition. The findings of the study by Wardoyo, Satrio, Narmaditya, and Wibowo (2021) demonstrated a positive and significant relationship between students' technology knowledge and their capacity for critical thought. They came to the conclusion that the fundamental rationale is that effective learning is created and, of course, students will feel comfortable when receiving it, when students' understanding is supported by the ability to use technology when learning to use smartphones. In fact, students gain technological knowledge that is specific to technological environments and enterprises, as well as knowledge of how and why things function. They gain knowledge about how to assess design concepts using functional modeling (Tanak, 2020). Furthermore, when technological content knowledge is always observed by the public senior high school TVL students during the resumption of face-to-face classes, they would have high critical thinking disposition. The result is associated with what Vladova et al. (2021) claim that technological content knowledge was found to be able to raise student achievement and proficiency. The 21st century demands technology mastery starting with technology knowledge. Students' learning behavior can be affected and their understanding can grow at the same time because they know how to use certain technologies appropriately. Additionally, Winstone, Nash, Parker and Rowntree (2017) demonstrated the positive and significant influence of technology content knowledge on students' critical thinking disposition improvement using integrated technology as a learning tool. Technology content knowledge further improves students' higher-order thinking, writing, and problem-solving abilities. For instance, the development of students' critical thinking abilities has resulted in an improvement in their performance in the science subject as a result of improving their technological content learning skills (Shehzadi et al., 2020).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the conclusions that were drawn out of the findings of the study. This section further offers recommendations as to how the findings of this study can improve practice. This study aimed to determine the extents of digital learning functionality and critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction during the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, this study sought to determine if relationship exists between the digital learning functionality and critical thinking disposition of public senior

high school TVL students, as well as the degree of their relationship. Moreover, this study sought to determine which of the students' digital learning functionality domains significantly influence their critical thinking disposition. This study utilized the descriptive-correlational design to determine the extent of digital learning functionality and critical thinking disposition and if they are significantly related. The respondents of this study were the selected one hundred fifty (150) public senior high school TVL students in Cluster 1, Division of Davao City who were selected using simple random sampling technique. The researcher used adopted survey questionnaires to collect the necessary information. Data collection involved strict compliance of ethical considerations. Mean, Pearson's r , and multiple regression were used to analyze the data that had been collected.

4.1. Findings—The extent of digital learning functionality of public senior high school TVL students is extensive. This means that the digital learning functionality of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction is oftentimes observed. The extent of critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students is extensive. This means that the critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction is oftentimes observed. The result also shows that there is a significant positive relationship between the digital learning functionality and critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students. Moreover, the degree of the relationship is high. This means that when the digital learning functionality of public senior high school TVL students is always observed, they would have high critical thinking disposition. Lastly, the result of the regression analysis shows that technology knowledge and technological content knowledge are the domains of digital learning functionality that significantly influenced the critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face classes.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn by the researcher: The digital learning functionality of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction is extensive. Though the learners

nowadays are digitally inclined and the digital platform was one of the most utilized learning modalities in the deliver of instruction during the distance education, still their technological literacy and skills need lots of attention to enhance. The critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students in the resumption of face-to-face instruction is extensive. It is evident that one of the challenges faced by the new generations of learners are their ability to think critically. With this, there is a need to amplify the efforts and exhaust the interventions by the educators to address this issue. The extent of critical thinking disposition of public senior high school TVL students would depend on their digital learning functionality. When their digital learning functionality is high, their skills to think critically would escalate, which is very important as one of the very important foundation towards attaining the 21st century skills. Moreover, it is evident that those public senior high school TVL students who have high technology knowledge and technological content would always manifest of having high critical thinking disposition.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the foregoing conclusions, the following are recommended:

The Department of Education should boost the implementation of programs related to improving the 21st literacy skills of learners, particularly by heightening the activities pertaining to digital learning functionality. This can be

done by allocating high budget on digital facilities in schools. Moreover, the Department of Education, Division of Davao City should sustain different intervention in upskilling teachers towards capsulating the technological skills and teaching strategies in the delivery the instruction to the learners. The schools may revisit their School Improvement Plan if programs related to digital learning functionality for the learners are given priority. These programs should be continuously monitored and assessed to maintain the effectivity of the implementation. Moreover, the Master Teachers should provide technical assistance to the teachers/ mentees especially in terms of technological skills to ensure that digital teaching in their classes are consistently practiced. The teachers in TVL track should undergo capacity building activities and attend professional advancement program to enhance their technological skills in teaching. Moreover, teachers should constantly provide activities that could enhance the critical thinking disposition of the learners. The Future Researchers may use this study as a reference to further investigate and explore other factors that may affect the critical thinking disposition of the senior high school TVL students.

5. References

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